

PARAMETRIC STUDY ON EFFECTIVE YOUNG'S MODULUS AND POISSON'S RATIO OF OPEN-CELL CARBON FOAM

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ABSTRACT

The emerging ultralightweight material, carbon foam, was modeled with three-dimensional microstructures to develop a basic understanding of the performance of open-cell foam materials. Because of the randomness and complexity of the microstructure of the carbon foam, representative cell ligaments were first characterized in detail at the microstructural level. In order to implement the inhomogeneous and anisotropic nature of material properties in the foam ligaments, we made the first attempt to use a finite element method to achieve such variation along the ligaments as well as at a nodal point where the ligaments meet.

We observed that the effective elastic properties of the foams were dominated by the bending mode associated with shear deformation. The effective Young's modulus of the foam was strongly influenced by the ligament moduli, but was hardly influenced by the ligament Poisson's ratio. The effective Poisson's ratio of the foam was practically independent of the ligament Young's modulus, but dependent on the ligament Poisson's ratio.

We performed a parametric study varying the orthotropic properties in different directions in the ligaments to assess how the microscopic properties in the ligaments affected the macroscopic bulk behavior. The prediction indicated that the effective Young's modulus of the carbon foam was more dependent on the transverse Young's modulus and the shear moduli of the foam ligaments, than on the ligament longitudinal Young's modulus. The parametric study also indicated that the effective Young's modulus could be significantly improved by increasing the ligament modulus in its mid-length, but nearly invariant with that at the nodal point where the ligaments join. Therefore, to optimize bulk moduli of carbon foam, appropriate processing schemes toward improving modulus in the middle section of the ligaments rather than at the nodal points are highly desirable.

KEY WORDS: Open-cell, Carbon foam, Effective bulk property, Microstructure, Finite element analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon foam is emerging as an ultralightweight and efficient thermal management material for many multifunctional applications, such as high-density electronics, hybrid diesel-electric vehicles, communication satellites, and advanced aircraft and spacecraft. Carbon foam was shown to demonstrate numerous unique properties that make it an attractive material for use as low-cost, lightweight, insulating, energy-absorbing structural components [1].

Figure 1 shows a microstructure of an open-cell carbon foam. Based on the minimum surface energy during the foaming process, the carbon foam microstructure is known to possess a tetrahedral

structure of the foam ligaments oriented approximately 109° to each other [2]. Investigation reveals that the graphitic alignment of the cell ligaments varies along its longitudinal (axial) direction. Processing parameters, such as temperature, pressure, etc., control the porosity and the graphitic alignment of the carbon foam, which in turn determine its geometries and material properties. With an ongoing research effort to investigate appropriate microstructural characterization techniques to correlate the foam microstructure with the processing parameters, the microstructural geometry and material properties of the foam, including mechanical elastic moduli, Poisson's ratio, thermal conductivity, etc., will be used for the mechanical and thermal analysis.

Figure 1. Microstructure of carbon foam.

A number of micromechanical models have been developed to describe the mechanical behavior of the cellular foams and thus to predict their effective properties [2-8]. Gibson and Ashby [5] found that the single most important structural characteristic of a cellular solid is its relative density $\bar{\rho} = \rho^* / \rho_s$ (or equivalently, porosity), which is the bulk density of the foam (ρ^*) divided by that of the solid of which it is made (ρ_s). They suggested an empirical formula for the effective Young's modulus (E^*) of the foam as follows:

$$\frac{E^*}{E_s} = C \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right)^n = C \bar{\rho}^n, \quad (1)$$

where E_s and ρ_s are the Young's modulus and density of the solid ligaments, respectively. The value of n generally lies in the range $1 \leq n < 4$, giving a wide range of properties at a given density. The linear dependence ($n=1$) of the Young's modulus on density is typical of foams that were modeled with straight ligaments under longitudinal compressive or tensile models of deformation [2, 4]. The quadratic dependence ($n=2$) is due to the bending nature of the ligament deformation [2, 5, 6]. Experimental evidence suggests that $n=2$ for open cells. Meanwhile, the Poisson's ratio has been thought to be independent of density [4, 5].

Existing theoretical formulae for prediction of the effective properties of the cellular foams have been derived from the fact that the solid properties in the foam ligaments were isotropic and homogeneous. However, we have observed from polarized optical microscopy that the ligaments of the carbon foam possessed anisotropic properties with varying properties along the ligament. The anisotropy is caused by alignment of graphitic layers in the ligaments, similar to that observed in the carbon/graphite fibers. The graphitic alignment is achieved by heat treatment at temperatures over 1000°C ; better graphitic alignment occurs with increasing heat-treatment temperature. For example, pure graphite contains perfect graphitic alignment between the layers. Therefore, to establish a realistic process-property relationship of carbon foams, it is necessary to incorporate the material property distribution in the foam ligaments in the model development.

Sihn and Roy [9] developed a tetrahedral three-dimensional geometry of the carbon foam ligaments based on a bubble-forming process. The unit cell consists of four ligaments oriented 109° to each other with varying cross-sectional area along their length. With the geometry known, the stress analysis can be performed with the microstructure of the carbon foam by applying appropriate boundary conditions. In this study, we will develop a numerical model for predicting the effective properties of the carbon foam with varying foam ligament properties along its length. The model will be developed based on using a finite element (FE) method applied to the tetrahedral three-dimensional unit-cell geometry of the carbon foam ligaments. The model will further be used to perform a

parametric study by varying the orthotropic properties in different directions in the ligaments to assess how the microscopic properties in the ligaments affected the macroscopic bulk behavior. Since selective ligament microstructure is expected to be achieved through an appropriate processing scheme, the present model containing the salient microstructural characteristics of carbon foam is expected to aid in establishing a process-property relationship of carbon foam so that application of specific optimal properties can be achieved through a suitable processing scheme.

PREDICTION METHOD OF EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF CARBON FOAMS

In view of the complexity of carbon foam microstructure, it may be realistic to consider a representative unit cell for the model development. The prediction of the effective elastic properties of the carbon foam was performed by applying appropriate boundary conditions to the unit cell geometry generated by Sihn and Roy [9]. FE mesh generation and FE analysis for the unit-cell model were performed with a commercial finite element software, ANSYS. The unit cell was loaded under a constant uniaxial strain in the loading direction, and constrained to prevent deformation in the other two perpendicular directions. The boundary condition of the foam ligaments equivalent to uniform uniaxial strain of the unit cell was achieved by applying a prescribed displacement boundary condition at nodal points on the tip surfaces of the ligaments, coinciding with the surfaces of the tetrahedron, as explained earlier. The values of the prescribed displacements in the loading direction varied with the location of the nodal points, whereas those in other directions perpendicular to the loading direction were set to zero. For example, if the loading was applied in the x -direction, the displacement values were $d_x = x/\varepsilon_x^o$, $d_y = 0$ and $d_z = 0$, where x and ε_x^o are the nodal coordinate and the applied constant strain, respectively.

Effective stress components ($\tilde{\sigma}_i$) of the tetrahedral unit cell were calculated by taking volumetric averages of resultant stress field over the volume of the tetrahedron, given by

$$\tilde{\sigma}_i = \frac{\sum_e \sigma_i^e v^e}{V_{tetra}} = \frac{\sum_e \sigma_i^e v^e}{V_{unit}} (1 - \varphi) \quad , \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, 6, \quad (2)$$

where σ_i^e and v^e are stress components and volume of the finite elements in the unit cell, respectively. The unit cells in the carbon foam are randomly oriented in three-dimensional space and are connected with each other at the tips of the ligaments. We assumed that the unit cells occupy the space with all possible orientations with equal probability, leading to isotropy in the bulk properties of the carbon foam. In this study we employed an orientation schemes with spherical zenithal (θ) and azimuthal (ϕ) angles. The volume average of the stress associated with the individual tetrahedral unit cell, being taken over all possible orientations, can be approximated by

$$\bar{\sigma}_i = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_\theta} \sum_{l=1}^{n_\phi} \tilde{\sigma}_i(\theta_k, \phi_l) \sin \phi_l \Delta\phi \Delta\theta}{\sum_{k=1}^{n_\theta} \sum_{l=1}^{n_\phi} \sin \phi_l \Delta\phi \Delta\theta}, \quad (3)$$

where $\theta_k = (2k-1) \Delta\theta/2$, $\phi_l = (2l-1) \Delta\phi/2$, $n_\theta = \pi/\Delta\theta$ and $n_\phi = 2\pi/\Delta\phi$. The effective Young's modulus (\bar{E}) and Poisson's ratio ($\bar{\nu}$) of the carbon foam were then calculated by the three-dimensional constitutive law of isotropic material, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{E} &= \frac{1}{\varepsilon_i^o} [\bar{\sigma}_i - \bar{\nu}(\bar{\sigma}_j + \bar{\sigma}_k)], \\ \bar{\nu} &= \frac{\bar{\sigma}_j}{\bar{\sigma}_i + \bar{\sigma}_k},\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_i$ is the volumetric average of stress components in the loading direction, and $\bar{\sigma}_j$ and $\bar{\sigma}_k$ are those in the other two directions perpendicular to the loading direction.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND PARAMETRIC STUDY

Effective Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio were calculated for the carbon foam for various densities with the present model. The prediction of effective properties was made based on both isotropic and anisotropic assumptions on the ligament properties. To understand the influence of the ligament properties on the bulk foam properties, the Young's modulus of the foam ligament was varied with the values of 7, 16 and 25 GPa. Note that the value 16 GPa was close to the transverse modulus of a pitch-based AS4 carbon fiber [10]. The solid Poisson's ratio of the ligament was assumed to be 0.2 or 0.33. The considered density of the carbon material was assumed to be 1.4 g/cm³, which is normally the density of carbonized carbon material heat-treated at about 1000°C but not graphitized. The calculation was made for open-cell carbon foams, whose densities are less than 0.31 g/cm³ [9].

Figure 2 (a) shows the effective Young's moduli predicted with the present model at various densities along with the limited available experimental data measured with carbon foam [11]. In this and subsequent figures, it will be understood that E and ν are those for the solid properties by omitting the subscript (s) for the solid properties, unless needed for clarity. The figure reveals that the ligament modulus significantly influencing the values of the effective bulk modulus, whereas the ligament Poisson's ratio essentially did not have any effect on the effective foam modulus. Therefore, it is important to know the solid properties (modulus in particular) of the ligaments to accurately predict the effective foam properties. The over-prediction of the measured effective modulus, using 16 GPa (transverse modulus of pitch-based AS4 fiber) as the ligament modulus, indicates that the current foaming process of the carbon foam does not achieve similar solid properties as the AS4 carbon fibers as of yet.

Figure 2 (b) shows the effective Poisson's ratios at the various densities with the present and other existing prediction methods. The present model predicted the effective Poisson's ratio of the carbon foam such that the Poisson's ratio approached 0.5 in the low-density limit; but as the density increased to 0.1 g/cm³, it decreased significantly, and then remained almost constant for densities higher than 0.1 g/cm³. Unlike the Young's modulus, the effective Poisson's ratio was nearly independent of the solid Young's modulus of the foam ligaments but affected by the solid (or ligament) Poisson's ratio. However, the influence on the bulk Poisson's ratio values was not as significant as that on the bulk Young's modulus. Therefore, as stated before, accurate determination of the solid Young's modulus of the foam ligaments is more important than that of the solid Poisson's ratio to accurately describe the bulk behavior of the carbon foam.

Figure 2. Effective Young's moduli and Poisson's ratio of carbon foam at various densities predicted with isotropic solid properties of foam ligaments. The solid Young's moduli of the foam ligaments varied with the values of 7, 16 and 25 GPa.

As stated earlier, the solid material properties of the carbon foam are not uniform but vary significantly point-by-point along the ligament length. Ideally, the carbon foam ligaments possess similar material characteristics of carbon fibers, whose superior properties are aligned with the longitudinal directions of the ligaments through graphitic alignments parallel to ligament length. Since the anisotropic solid properties of the carbon foam ligament are not well determined, in order to perform a sensitivity study we made three assumptions as follows: (1) the foam ligaments possessed transversely anisotropic properties, whose longitudinal properties parallel to length-direction of the ligament significantly differ from the transverse properties perpendicular to the ligament length direction; (2) ligament longitudinal and transverse major Poisson's ratios were assumed as $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.33$ and $\nu_{23} = 0.5$, respectively; and (3) ligament longitudinal (G_{12} and G_{13}) and transverse (G_{23}) shear moduli were calculated by

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = \frac{E_2}{2(1 + \nu_{21})} \quad \text{and} \quad G_{23} = \frac{E_2}{2(1 + \nu_{23})}, \quad (5)$$

where $\nu_{21} = \nu_{12} E_2 / E_1$. Two cases of the sensitivity study were considered: (1) the values of the transverse modulus of the ligament varied from 10 GPa to 40 GPa, while keeping the value of the longitudinal modulus fixed at 200 GPa, and (2) the value of the longitudinal modulus varied from 20 GPa to 1000 GPa, while keeping the value of the transverse modulus fixed at 20 GPa.

Figures 3 and 4 show the sensitivity of the values of the effective Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the foam possessing the transversely isotropic ligament properties, as a function of foam density. Results with the anisotropic material properties were compared with those with the isotropic ones. As shown in Figure 3 (a), the Young's moduli with the anisotropic ligament properties of $E_1 = 200$ GPa and $E_2 = 20$ GPa yielded similar prediction as that with the isotropic ligament property of $E = 25$ GPa. Furthermore, the data in Figure 3 (a) imply that the effective Young's moduli of the carbon foam are highly dependent on the transverse modulus of the foam ligaments. Meanwhile, Figure 4 (a) shows that the effect of the ligament longitudinal moduli on the values of the foam effective moduli was less significant than that due to the ligament transverse moduli. Higher dependency on the ligament transverse moduli than on the longitudinal ones implied that the primary ligament deformation mode is bending associated with shear mode of deformation than simply the axial deformation.

Figures 3 (b) and 4 (b) show the values of the predicted Poisson's ratio of the carbon foam as a function of foam density. As in the case of the isotropic ligament properties, the present prediction yielded nearly constant Poisson's ratios unless the carbon foam was of low density. Unlike the Young's modulus, the Poisson's ratio was nearly independent of both the longitudinal and transverse moduli of the foam ligament, as shown in both figures.

(a) Effective Young's modulus

(b) Effective Poisson's ratio

Figure 3. Effective Young's moduli and Poisson's ratio of carbon foam at various densities predicted with isotropic and anisotropic solid properties of foam ligaments. The in-plane shear moduli were assumed to be proportional to transverse Young's modulus of the foam ligaments. Longitudinal modulus of the ligament was fixed at 200 GPa, while transverse modulus varied from 10 GPa to 40 GPa.

(a) Effective Young's modulus

(b) Effective Poisson's ratio

Figure 4. Effective Young's moduli and Poisson's ratio of carbon foam at various densities predicted with isotropic and anisotropic solid properties of foam ligaments. The in-plane shear moduli were assumed to be proportional to transverse Young's modulus of the foam ligaments. Transverse modulus of the ligament was fixed at 20 GPa, while longitudinal modulus varied from 20 GPa to 1000 GPa.

In the above parametric study, the ligament shear moduli were assumed to vary proportional to that of ligament transverse modulus (Eq. (5)). As a result, the effect of ligament longitudinal shear moduli on the bulk effective properties of foam could not be separated from that of the ligament transverse modulus. To assess the effect of ligament shear moduli on foam bulk behavior, another parametric study was performed where the ligament material orthotropy was assumed to be such that the longitudinal shear moduli (G_{12} and G_{13}) were dependent on the longitudinal Young's modulus rather than the transverse Young's modulus as follows:

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = \frac{E_1}{2(1+\nu_{12})}. \quad (6)$$

Contrary to the previous cases, the effective Young's modulus in this case depended significantly on both the longitudinal and the transverse moduli of the foam ligaments, as shown in Figures 5 and 6. Any variation of E_1 in this parametric study resulted in proportional variation in both G_{12} and G_{13} (see Eq. (6)). In the prior parametric study (G_{12} , and G_{13} were functions of E_2 , but not functions of E_1), the bulk effective modulus was found to be strongly sensitive to E_2 , but not to E_1 , which implied that the effective modulus was also possibly sensitive to the ligament longitudinal shear moduli G_{12} and G_{13} as well. Now, from the data in Figures 5 and 6, as obtained by making G_{12} and G_{13} dependent on E_1 , it can be inferred that the observed sensitivity of the effective foam modulus was primarily due to the ligament longitudinal shear moduli (G_{12} , and G_{13}). Therefore, it can be deduced that the effective Young's modulus is greatly affected by the transverse Young's modulus and the shear moduli, but less significantly by the longitudinal Young's modulus of the foam ligament. A similar observation was also made for the effective Poisson's ratio. Therefore, improving the transverse Young's modulus and shear moduli of carbon foam ligaments appears to benefit the effective bulk modulus of carbon foam much more than the ligament longitudinal modulus.

Figure 5. Effective Young's moduli and Poisson's ratio of carbon foam at various densities predicted with isotropic and anisotropic solid properties of foam ligaments. The in-plane shear moduli were assumed to be proportional to longitudinal Young's modulus of the foam

ligaments. Longitudinal modulus of the ligament was fixed at 200 GPa, while transverse modulus varied from 10 GPa to 40 GPa.

Figure 6. Effective Young's moduli and Poisson's ratio of carbon foam at various densities predicted with isotropic and anisotropic solid properties of foam ligaments. The in-plane shear moduli were assumed to be proportional to longitudinal Young's modulus of the foam ligaments. Transverse modulus of the ligament was fixed at 20 GPa, while longitudinal modulus varied from 20 GPa to 1000 GPa.

Polarized optical microscopic observation indicated that the material properties varied along the foam ligaments. Typically, due to better graphitic alignment near the ligament mid-length than that at the nodes (where ligaments meet), the modulus in the middle of the ligaments is expected to be higher than that of the nodes. This observed phenomenon is essentially due to the nature of the foam-forming process and post-foam heat-treatment conditions. To analyze the effect of ligament property gradient, we partitioned the unit cell of the carbon foam ligaments into four segments as shown in Figure 7, and varied the material properties of a few partitions. We assumed that the ligament properties were isotropic and constant within each partition. A notation $\{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4\}$ is used for a collection of Young's moduli of the first through the fourth segments, whose annotations (numberings) are shown in Figure 7. With base material properties of $E_s = 7$ GPa and $\nu_s = 0.33$, the Young's moduli of the specific partitions were varied from 3 GPa to 11 GPa. Four different cases were considered by varying the values of the following selective partitions: (1) only segment 4 (node); (2) segments 3 and 4; (3) only segment 1 (middle); and (4) segments 1 and 2, while keeping the moduli of other partitions fixed to the base value of 7 GPa.

Figure 8 shows the effective Young's modulus of carbon foam with the varying Young's modulus of the selected partitions in the foam ligaments. The values of the Poisson's ratios were not shown here because they are hardly affected by the property variation along the ligaments. The bulk density was chosen as $\rho_s = 0.1$ g/cm³. Note that the following conclusions were applicable for other densities as well. The results shown in Figure 8 were normalized by that of the case of $\{7, 7, 7, 7\}$. As shown in the case of $\{7, 7, 7, E_4\}$, the moduli at the nodal point do not have much effect on the bulk modulus. However, the property variation near the mid-length of the ligaments affected the effective Young's modulus significantly. The variation of the modulus near the mid-length of the ligament from 7 GPa to 11 GPa caused 40% increase of the bulk Young's modulus. Therefore, to optimize bulk moduli of carbon foam, appropriate processing schemes toward improving modulus in the middle section of the ligaments rather than at the nodal points are highly desirable.

Figure 7. A representative unit cell of carbon foam partitioned into four segments.

Figure 8. Effective Young's moduli and Poisson's ratio of carbon foam ($\rho_s = 0.1 \text{g/cm}^3$) with property variation along the foam ligaments. $\{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4\}$ denotes a collection of Young's moduli of the first through the fourth segments, whose annotations (numberings) are shown in Figure 7.

SUMMARY

The emerging ultralightweight material, carbon foam, was modeled with the three-dimensional microstructures to develop a basic understanding of the performance of open-cell foam materials. Since selective ligament microstructure is expected to be achieved through an appropriate processing scheme, the present model containing the salient microstructural characteristics of carbon foam is

expected to aid in establishing a process-property relationship of carbon foam so that application of specific optimal properties can be achieved through a suitable processing scheme.

We observed that the effective elastic properties of the foams were dominated by the bending mode associated with shear deformation. The effective Young's modulus of the foam was strongly influenced by the ligament moduli but was hardly influenced by the ligament Poisson's ratio. The effective Poisson's ratio was, however, practically independent of the ligament Young's modulus, but dependent on the ligament Poisson's ratio. Further, the influence of the ligament properties on the bulk Poisson's ratio results was not as significant as that on the bulk Young's modulus. Therefore, accurate determination of the solid properties (modulus in particular) of the foam ligaments is important to accurately predict the effective bulk properties.

The prediction indicated that the effective Young's modulus of the carbon foam was dependent more on the transverse Young's modulus and the shear moduli of the foam ligaments, but less significantly on the ligament longitudinal Young's modulus. Similar observation was also made for the effective Poisson's ratio. Thus, the process optimization for the carbon foam should be emphasized more on improving the transverse and shear properties of the foam ligaments rather than the longitudinal properties. Further, the effective Young's modulus was significantly improved by increasing the solid modulus in the middle of the foam ligaments, but nearly invariant with that at the nodal point where the ligaments met. Therefore, to optimize bulk moduli of carbon foam, appropriate processing schemes toward improving modulus in the middle section of the ligaments rather than at the nodal points are highly desirable.

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